

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_5_1	
Title	REDS (Reciprocal Environmental Decision Support)
Category	Socio-cultural/Environmental/Spatial
Purpose of the method	Improve land-use decisions at central levels (authorities and scientists) and local levels (communities and individual land managers) by improving quality of and access to models of effects of land-use change. This is achieved by Citizen Science and Environmental Decision Support being combined in a novel way (see Kenward et al., 2024).
Effort in time	A user can report data to scientists and reciprocally receive automated advice within minutes; but the process of the user-inputted data leading to better support could take months or longer.
Number of objects investigated	Potentially limitless. In the example of the Arne Case Study, we might expect a few hundred reports from the public.
Data format	Spatial data is collected from users, for example, locations of local micro-habitats and species sightings.
Description	<p>Consider two traditional forms of one-way data flow. Citizen Science is primarily from citizens to scientists. Environmental Decision Support (EDS) is primarily from scientists to citizens. So that EDS can be tailored to the specific needs of citizens with specific local circumstances, they typically describe their local circumstances, but this information is not retained. REDS closes this loop: citizens provide data to scientists, which is useful to the scientists and allows them to update their models, but in return, the citizens receive tailored EDS.</p> <p>An example of how this will be used is from the Arne Case Study which aims to re-establish native red squirrels. Control of grey squirrels will be facilitated by citizen reports of sighting locations for grey squirrels. In return, citizens will receive tailored advice about how their gardens could be improved to better support the reds, for example by maximizing native tree species corridors.</p>
Basic Literature	Kenward, R., Ewald, J., Casey, C., & Kenward, B. (2024) Reciprocal Environmental Decision Support (REDS): tailored support in return for data. <i>Working paper</i> . Available at https://esug.sycl.net/file_link/00064/Reciprocal_Environmental_Decision_Support_(REDS)_638628676574933256.pdf
Contact person within the project	First contact: Ben Kenward, ESUG. Other contacts: Robert Kenward, ESUG; Nick Case, Anatrack.